

COOPERATION RELATIONS BETWEEN UZBEKISTAN AND TURKMENISTAN

Ismailov Tokhirjon Khushnudbek ugli

Mamun University, teacher

E-mail: tohirjon_ismailov@mamunedu.uz

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8571-3653>

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There is great interest on both sides in the art and literature of the two sister countries of Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan. Representatives of science, education and culture of the two countries closely cooperate and actively participate in all events held in the territory of Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan.

Uzbeks and Turkmens are the inheritors and keepers of the richest cultural and scientific traditions. The works of great poets and thinkers Alisher Navoi and Makhtumkuli are the common heritage of our peoples. The opening of a street named after Makhtumkuli and its bas-relief in Tashkent, and the establishment of the People's House are a bright symbol of strong friendship, unity and cultural closeness. In turn, a street named after Alisher Navoi was opened in the capital of Turkmenistan.

All necessary conditions have been created for the development of national traditions and culture of 200,000 Turkmens living in Uzbekistan. Six cultural centers coordinated by the Republican Turkmen Cultural Center and the Uzbekistan-Turkmenistan Friendship Society play an important role in strengthening the cultural ties between the Uzbek and Turkmen peoples.

In order to preserve and promote the culture and traditions of the Turkmen people, cultural and educational events are held in our country, and 45 schools are operating where education is conducted in the Turkmen language, where 8 thousand children study.

Education is one of the important areas of cooperation between the two countries. Today, Nukus State Pedagogical Institute named after Ajinyoz has a faculty for training teachers for primary grades in Turkmen language, Karakalpak State University has a faculty of Turkmen philology. Mutual cooperation in the field of education, without a doubt, makes a worthy contribution to the process of enriching cultural cooperation, serves communication between young people, and strengthens our brotherly relations.

Relations between Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan are characterized by close interests in areas such as regional trade, development of transit and energy potential, regional stability and security.

The countries are paying special attention to strengthening bilateral relations in almost all spheres of mutual cooperation and are making significant efforts. The decisions made between the two countries contribute to the further expansion of the strategic partnership between the two brotherly nations and strengthening of close relations.

Mutual support and coordination in the joint promotion of initiatives, as well as the efforts of the leaders of Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan to strengthen mutually beneficial cooperation at the bilateral and regional level, will certainly serve to maintain peace and security in the region. It is also considered an important factor for the stable development of the entire Central Asia.

Uzbekistan attaches priority to strengthening cooperation relations with neighboring Turkmenistan. This cooperation, based on national traditions, common religion, language and cultural unity, goes back to deep historical roots. In the mutual cooperation between Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan, a number of directions in the near and medium term are of priority. At this point, it is important to consider trade-economic and investment cooperation, expansion of industrial cooperation between the agro-industrial complex, automotive and light industry, transport and communication industries, as well as the involvement of companies of the two countries in the implementation of large infrastructure projects in the territory of Uzbekistan and Turkmenistan as a driver of economic cooperation. Also, both countries are interested in the realization of transit potential, as well as in the development of mutual trade between countries and regions. The integration of the communication systems of the two countries allows not only to carry out cargo transportation through the territory of Uzbekistan to Turkmenistan and vice versa, but also to enter the markets of the Near and Middle East in the shortest possible time.

At the same time, close cooperation between the countries in the region in water management, ecology and environmental protection issues can be said to be exemplary and the most effective.

The joint statement of the presidents adopted in 2022 noted the importance of continuing constructive dialogue in the field of fair and rational use of water resources of transboundary rivers of Central Asia.

It is also interested in creating favorable conditions for the development of its native language, culture, traditions and customs, and supporting the mutual translation of classic literature and folk works, while realizing its historical responsibility to preserve and strengthen cultural-humanitarian ties and friendship ties.

In addition, the parties have a common understanding of achieving peace and stability in Afghanistan and providing humanitarian assistance to the Afghan people, contributing to maintaining trade-economic, transport logistics and energy relations with this country, implementing infrastructure projects, and ensuring comprehensive international cooperation.

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